

IMPROVING A2 LEVEL STUDENTS' SPEAKING SKILLS WITH THE HELP OF THE DUOLINGO PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This article explores improving A2 level students speaking skills with the help of the Duolingo program. In contemporary world using new technologies is not a big problem for everyone because all of parts of people know how to use smartphones. So downloading Duolingo is easy and it gives more opportunities for learning foreign languages. Using the Duolingo program for improving speaking skills is more effective and showed results in 2 days

One language sets you in a corridor for life. Two languages open every door

along the way. (Frank Smith)

Duolingo, (/ˌdjuːoʊˈlɪŋɡoʊ/ (DEW-oh-LING-goh) is a language learning website and mobile app where users learn using “networks” tailored to the target language, with specific “skills” to practice vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation through repetition. Skills-based exercises may include written translation, reading comprehension, speaking comprehension, and short story exercises. As of June 2021, Duolingo offers 103 language courses in 40 languages (but does not yet include Uzbek). The Duolingo platform has over 500 million registered users.

Users in CEFR-aligned courses can use the Duolingo Score to gauge their level of competency in the language they are studying. A detailed evaluation of a student's language proficiency and knowledge is given by Duolingo Score. (The score method used by DET is comparable. Duolingo scores range from 0 to 130 in the most advanced CEFR-aligned courses (French, English, and Spanish) (Yang, Kevin October 23, 2024). According to the Council of Europe's Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR), which defines many language levels, English level A2 is the second level of the language. This level could be characterized as "basic" in ordinary conversation, as in "I speak basic English." "Elementary" is the official level descriptor in the CEFR, and it implies "the foundation." Students at this level are proficient in the fundamentals of English and can express simple demands. A2 level students may improve their speaking skills with the gamification method to the C1 level.

The gamification of the learning approach uses points, prizes, and interactive lessons with spaced repetition to encourage users. The software encourages daily, brief sessions for practice that are phased in and consistent. Duolingo allows students to interact with the course material and learn by doing. Because the lessons are short, users can learn in digestible portions. With lessons that include stories, interactive exercises, tests, and translation, Duolingo takes a gamified approach to education. (Additionally, it makes use of an algorithm that can deliver tailored feedback and suggestions based on the individual learner. Duolingo offers a competitive environment, including leagues, where users may compete against randomly chosen global player groups consisting of up to 30 participants. Leagues: Amethyst, Pearl, Obsidian, Diamond, Sapphire, Ruby, Emerald, Silver, Gold, and Bronze. The amount of experience points accumulated in a week determines a league's ranking. In Duolingo, badges stand for accomplishments obtained by fulfilling particular goals. Additionally, users can design their avatars.

On iOS and Android, Duolingo has a widget option. Originally, the widget functionality was a project for Duolingo's yearly hackathon. Kyle Ruane created the 39 illustrations for the iOS widget, which was meant to serve as an additional daily reminder to finish lessons. The user's daily streak is displayed at the top of the widgets.

Every Duolingo lesson finished will go toward the user's daily streak. The app uses fire as the visual metaphor for the daily streak. Users can keep up streaks with up to five pals using Duolingo's "Friend Streak" feature. [Streaks supports the development of a regular learning habit by promoting constant daily practice. The application uses a customized bandit algorithm system (later the A/B tested variant recovering difference softmax method) to decide which user will receive a reminder each day.

In addition, Duolingo provides the Duolingo ABC literacy program for kids and the Duolingo English Test, an online language test. With optional premium services like Super Duolingo and Duolingo Max, which are ad-free and offer more features, the company operates on a freemium model. With optional premium services like Super Duolingo and Duolingo Max, which are ad-free and offer more features, the company operates on a freemium model. Duolingo also owns and operates Pittsburgh's Duo's Taqueria, a Mexican taco joint. Duolingo also owns and operates Pittsburgh's Duo's Taqueria, a Mexican taco joint.

Use the most downloaded educational software in the world to pick up a new language! The entertaining, free program Duolingo offers short, bite-sized lessons in over 40 languages. Practice writing, speaking, reading, and listening to improve your grammar and vocabulary.

Duolingo, created by language experts and adored by hundreds of millions of learners worldwide, helps you get ready for authentic conversations in a variety of languages, including English, French, Chinese, Italian, German, and Spanish. You can now learn music and math the Duolingo way! In this math course, hone your mental math skills and develop practical math abilities, such as calculating tips and recognizing patterns. No instrument is needed to take our music course, which teaches you how to read music and perform well-

known songs on your device. Whether you're learning for your brain health, family, friends, job, education, or travel, you'll love Duolingo.

Why use Duolingo?

- Duolingo is entertaining and useful. Fun characters and game-like lessons keep you inspired to develop strong language, math, and musical abilities.
- Duolingo is effective. Duolingo was created by learning specialists and uses a science-based teaching approach that has been shown to promote long-term memory retention.
- Monitor your development. When you make practicing a daily habit, you can use fun rewards and accomplishments to work toward your learning objectives!
- Become one of the 300+ million learners. With competitive Leaderboards, you may stay inspired while learning alongside our international community.
- All classes are free. Portuguese, Turkish, Dutch, Irish, Danish, Swedish, Ukrainian, Esperanto, Polish, Greek, Hungarian, Norwegian, Hebrew, Welsh, Arabic, Latin, Hawaiian, Scottish Gaelic, Vietnamese, Korean, Japanese, English, and even High Valyrian are among the languages you can learn. Now, take advantage of our newest courses to learn music and math!

What the world is saying about Duolingo:

"Far and away the best language-learning app." –The Wall Street Journal

"This free app and website is among the most effective language-learning methods I've tried... lessons come in the form of brief challenges – speaking, translating, answering multiple-choice questions – that keep me coming back for more." –The New York Times

"Duolingo may hold the secret to the future of education." – TIME Magazine

"...Duolingo is cheerful, lighthearted and fun..." - Forbes

"Our favorite language app..." - CNET

Try Super Duolingo for free for 14 days if you enjoy Duolingo! Get entertaining benefits like Unlimited Hearts and Monthly Streak Repair while learning a language quickly and without advertisements.

Payment will be sent to your Apple account if you decide to buy Super Duolingo, and your account will be charged for renewal 24 hours before the current period expires. After purchase, you can go to your preferences in the App Store and disable auto-renewal at any time. If a free trial period is available, all unused time will be lost when the user, if appropriate, buys a subscription to that magazine.

In conclusion, improving communication skills with the Duolingo program is more effective not only for A2 level students but also for all people. Doing more practice, correcting mistakes, attending gamification competitions, and spending time with Duolingo's characters which are Lucy, Eddy, Junior, Lily, Lin, Oscar and others are more useful for growing up levels. In addition, Duolingo has a language assessment test system and this may help you to study TOP 5500 Universities or working foreign countries.

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